

grains better. 3) The amount of nitrogen applied is not excessive. Too much nitrogen leads to excessive vegetative growth, droopy leaves, lodging, increased disease and insect damage, and reduced availability of carbohydrates for grain-filling.

The number of secondary branches and spikelets increased by 11.5-19.0% when nitrogen was applied at the primordial panicle stage. Thus proper nitrogen application may increase the number of filled grains per panicle. It

increased dry panicle weight by 13.0-18.0%.

Use of nitrogen increased the respiratory intensity of primordial panicles by 0.004-0.040 mg CG /g panicle per hour, perhaps because treated plants grow stronger than untreated plants.

The total nitrogen content in the leaf blade was increased by 0.27-1.0% with nitrogen application. That increased photosynthetic activity and photosynthetic products, resulting in more normal branches and spikelets and thus

higher grain yield.

The contents of starch and sugars accumulated in the leaf sheath and stem of the treated plant were higher (about 14.1% and 17.4%, respectively) than in the control plants. Such assimilated carbohydrates contribute to the primordial panicle and thus increase grain yields.

Experiments using ^{14}C and ^{32}P show that the assimilation of ^{14}C and ^{32}P distributed among the middle and the lower parts of the developed panicle spikelets increased yields (Table 2). ■

Increased productivity in rice through inhibition of photorespiration

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Rice, a photorespiring plant (C3-type), loses much of its yield through photorespiration. Treatments with some inhibitors of photorespiration may increase the yield of this crop. In an experiment to test this hypothesis, neutralized aqueous solutions (10^{-3}M) of three photorespiratory inhibitors — isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH), sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO_3), and L-glutamic acid — were foliarly sprayed on the rice variety NC1281 at preflowering and postflowering stages and yield parameters were recorded. The yield parameters included fertility percentage, sterility percentage, grain weight per plant, thousand-grain weight, and grain-straw ratio.

Photorespiratory inhibitors applied at either the preflowering or postflowering stage markedly improved yield parameters and yield per plant (see table). The postflowering treatments showed better effects on yield parameters than the pre-

Effects of photorespiratory inhibitors on some yield parameters and yield of rice (NC1281), West Bengal, India.

Treatment (10^{-3}M)	Ripened grains (%)	Sterile grains (%)	Grain wt ^a (g/plant)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Grain-straw ratio
<i>Preflowering stage (145 days after sowing)</i>					
Control	86.27	13.73	16.20	26.49	0.345
INH	86.54	13.46	20.50 (+ 26.5)	26.52	0.357
NaHCO_3	87.22	12.78	17.30 (+ 6.8)	26.53	0.389
L-glutamic acid	85.38	14.62	16.00 (- 1.2)	26.45	0.340
<i>Postflowering stage (157 days after sowing)</i>					
INH	88.29	11.71	22.10 (+ 36.4)	26.55	0.452
NaHCO_3	87.32	12.68	21.00 (+ 29.6)	26.45	0.378
L-glutamic acid	86.43	13.57	20.00 (+ 23.4)	26.44	0.299

^aFigures within parentheses indicate percentage increases (+) or decreases (-) in yield in relation to the control.

flowering treatments and increased yield per plant considerably over the control. Among the inhibitors used, INH (inhibitor of glycolate pathway) was the most effective; it was followed by NaHCO_3 (inhibitor of RuBP carboxylase-oxygenase). L-glutamic acid (inhibitor of glycolate pathway), when applied at preflowering stage, slightly inhibited yield, but when applied at postflowering stage, significantly increased yield and other

yield parameters. The increase in yield could be ascribed to increased ripened grains and lower sterility. Thousand-grain weight of treated plants did not, however, vary distinctly from the control. The grain-straw ratio was positively correlated with grain weight per plant. Thus, some suitable photorespiratory inhibitors applied at a particular developmental stage of the plant could increase rice yield significantly. ■

A simple method for studying temperature and relative humidity within the rice plant canopy

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The conventional hygrothermograph measures the temperature-humidity levels in a given field, but not the actual microclimate between the tillers and areas where propagules of disease or insect pest organisms begin to develop. Equipment to measure such *microenvironmental* climates exists, but is difficult

to procure and unsafe in most Asian fields.

We have tested a simple system to measure the atmospheric moisture and temperature between tillers of rice clumps with several replications. A weighing bottle with 1 ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 (AR) is weighed with its